

Synthesis of novel rosin-based 3,4-disubstituted pyrazoles via 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of diazomethane with functionalized allenoate

Ilshat M. Sakhautdinov, Aynur M. Gumerov*, Rauilya N. Malikova, Akhnaif A. Fatykhov and Marat S. Yunusov

Ufa Institute of Chemistry, Ufa Research Centre, Russian Academy of Sciences,
Prospect Oktyabrya, 71, 450054, Ufa, Russian Federation

E-mail : aygumer@mail.ru

Manuscript received online 19 June 2015, accepted 21 October 2016

Abstract : Synthesis of 3,4-disubstituted 1*H*-pyrazoles based on maleopimaric acid (MPA) is described. 1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition of diazomethane with allenoates bearing maleopimaric acid methyl ester moiety afforded novel pyrazole derivatives with good regioselectivity in moderate yields.

Keywords : Allenes, pyrazoles, 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition, allenoates, maleopimaric acid, rosin.

Introduction

In the past decades, pyrazole, a five-membered heterocycle containing two adjacent nitrogen atoms, became one of the most important frameworks due to its presence in a number of molecules that possess a wide range of pharmaceutical activities¹⁻³. Several pyrazole-containing compounds such as celecoxib⁴, rimonabant⁵ and viagra⁶ have been successfully commercialized as medicines. In addition, the maleopimaric acid (MPA), the Diels-Alder adduct of rosin with maleic anhydride, is also a prominent scaffold in lot of bioactive molecules. Many MPA-based compounds have been reported to exhibit versatile bioactivities, such as antiulcer, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and antitumor activities⁷⁻¹⁰. Keeping this in view, we choose the methyl maleopimarate (MMP) as one of the substituents about the central pyrazole ring to synthesize novel 3,4-disubstituted 1*H*-pyrazoles bearing diterpene resin acid moiety starting from readily available natural product-rosin.

Results and discussion

MMP **1**, obtained from rosin according to the reported procedure¹¹, was treated with glycine, β -alanine, γ -aminobutyric acid in DMF to yield *N*-substituted amino acids **2a-c**, in 63, 68 and 72%. Olefination of *in situ*

generated ketenes **3a-c** from corresponding acids **2a-c**, with methyl (triphenylphosphoranylidene)acetate afforded allenoates **4a-c** in yields 63, 67 and 70%, respectively¹² (Scheme 1).

The structures of compounds **4a-c** were established from NMR data spectra. There are characteristic signals for allenic terminal C^{2'} and C^{4'} carbon atoms at δ 96.13 and 91.17 ppm (**4a**); δ 90.16 and 89.7 ppm (**4b**); δ 91.86 and 88.56 ppm (**4c**) in ¹³C NMR. Furthermore, the characteristic allene central carbon atom C^{3'} appears at δ 210.37 ppm (**4a**), δ 212.89 ppm (**4b**) and δ 212.44 ppm for (**4c**), respectively.

Cycloaddition reaction of allenoates **4a-c** with five-fold excess of diazomethane in the presence of equimolar quantity of Et₃N afforded 3,4-disubstituted 1*H*-pyrazoles **5a-c** in 39, 51 and 46% yields (Scheme 1). The reaction occurs regioselectively with the C-N bond cleavage at the α -position to the ester group^{13,14}. Complete spectra assignments of the ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of all synthesized compounds were established by 2D NMR techniques, namely COSY, HSQC, HMBC and NOESY.

Thus, in HMBC NMR spectra of pyrazole **5a** there are cross peaks of the methylene group protons at C1'' with imide carbons C1 and C3, two quaternary carbons

Scheme 1

C3', C4' and C5' carbon of pyrazole ring (Fig. 1). Other relevant spectra data of **5a** included correlations of the pyrazole ring proton of C5' at δ 7.57 with carbons C3', C4', as well as with methylene group carbon C1'', and

Fig. 1. Selected HMBC correlations for compound **5a**.

there is no correlation with C6' carbon. The ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of **5b** and **5c** contained signals similar to those of compound **5a**.

Conclusion

In conclusion, for the first time, introduction of the diterpene resin acid moiety into the pyrazole ring position 4 was performed via 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of diazomethane with functionalized allenates, as a key step. Novel 3,4-disubstituted 1*H*-pyrazoles were achieved with good regioselectivity in moderate yields.

Experimental

The infrared spectra were obtained on a Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectrometer (Shimadzu IRprestige-21). The ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AM-500 spectrometer at 500.13 and 125.76 MHz, respectively, using TMS as internal standard. The progress of reactions was monitored by TLC. Mass spectra were recorded on a LCMS-2010EV liquid chromatograph mass spectrometer (Shimadzu) in atmospheric pressure chemical ionization mode (APCI). Elemental analysis was carried out using a EURO EA-3000 CHN element analyzer. Melting points were measured with a Buetius apparatus. The products were isolated by column chromatography on silica gel (40–100 and 100–160 μm; Chemapol).

General procedure for the synthesis of MMP imides (2a-c) :

A mixture of 10 mmol of MMP and 15 mmol of amino acid in 25 ml DMF was heated under reflux. After MMP consumed (about 5 h), the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, distilled water is added and the precipitate filtered off. The solid was washed with distilled water, dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ and dried over anhydrous MgSO₄. The product was purified by column chromatography using CHCl₃-acetone (9 : 1) as eluent.

General procedure for the synthesis of the allenates 4a-c by Wittig reaction :

1 g of an acid **2a-c** was dispersed in 10 mL of anhydrous C₆H₆, five-fold excess of SOCl₂ was added, and the mixture was heated for 3 h under reflux. The solvent and excess SOCl₂ was distilled off on a rotary evapora-

tor, and the residue (acid chloride) was used without additional purification. An equimolar amount of Et₃N was added to a solution of methyl (triphenylphosphoranylidene)acetate in CH₂Cl₂, the mixture was cooled to -10 °C, and a cold solution of acid chloride was slowly added dropwise. The mixture was stirred for 0.5 h and kept at 0 °C for 6 h, then solvent was evaporated, and the residue was subjected to the purification by silica-gel column chromatography using petroleum ether-EtOAc (7 : 3) as eluent.

General procedure for the synthesis of the pyrazoles 5a-c from allenates 4a-c :

A cold solution (0 °C) of 0.5 g of allenates **4a-c** in 20 mL of CH₂Cl₂ was combined with an equimolar amount of Et₃N, and a six-fold excess of a freshly prepared solution of diazomethane in CH₂Cl₂ was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was stirred for 4 h at room temperature. The solvent was removed, and the reaction products were separated by column chromatography on silica gel using petroleum ether-EtOAc (1 : 1) as eluent.

Acknowledgement

The work was sponsored by a grant of the Russian Scientific Foundation No. 14-13-01307. Informational support was provided by RFBR Grant No. 13-00-14056. Spectral analysis was performed on equipment of the Khimiya CCU, IOC, USC, RAS.

References

1. S. Fustero, M. Sanchez-Rosello, P. Barrio and A. Simon-Fuentes, *Chem. Rev.*, 2011, **111**, 6984.
2. M. K. A. Ibrahim, A. M. El-Reedy, M. S. El-Gharib and A. M. Farag, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 345.
3. R. N. Mahajan, F. H. Havaladar and P. S. Fernandes, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 245.
4. L. M. Oh, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2006, **47**, 7943.
5. X. Deng and N. S. Mani, *Org. Lett.*, 2008, **10**, 1307.
6. N. K. Terrett, A. S. Bell, D. Brown and P. Ellis, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 1996, **6**, 1819.
7. O. B. Kazakova, E. V. Tret'yakova, O. S. Kukovinets, G. A. Tolstikov, T. I. Nazyrov, I. V. Chudov and A. F. Ismagilova, *Bioorg. Khim.*, 2010, **36**, 762.
8. J. Wang, Y. P. Chen, K. Yao, P. A. Wilbon, W. Zhang, L. Ren, J. Zhou, M. Nagarkatti, C. Wang, F. Chu, X. He, A.

- W. Decho and C. Tang, *Chem. Commun.*, 2012, **48**, 916.
9. G. Y. Yao, M. Y. Ye, R. Z. Huang, Y. J. Li, Y. T. Zhu, Y. M. Pan, Z. X. Liao and H. S. Wang, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2013, **24**, 6755.
10. E. V. Tret'yakova, I. E. Smirnova, O. B. Kazakova, G. A. Tolstikov, N. P. Yavorskaya, I. S. Golubeva, R. B. Pugacheva, G. N. Apryshko and V. V. Poroikov, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2014, **22**, 6481.
11. X. Q. Liu, W. B. Xin and J. W. Zhang, *Green Chem.*, 2009, **11**, 1018.
12. I. M. Sakhautdinov, A. M. Gumerov, G. G. Gibadullina, O. V. Zakir'yanova and M. S. Yunusov, *Chem. Nat. Compd.*, 2015, **51**, 332.
13. I. M. Sakhautdinov, A. M. Gumerov, I. R. Batyrshin, A. A. Fatykhov, K. Yu. Suponitsky and M. S. Yunusov, *Heterocycles*, 2014, **89**, 641.
14. I. M. Sakhautdinov, I. R. Batyrshin, A. A. Fatykhov, V. M. Yumabaeva, K. Yu. Suponitsky, M. Yu. Antipin and M. S. Yunusov, *J. Struct. Chem.*, 2013, **54**, 383.